

One Hundred Years of Solicitude: A Path Constitution Analysis of Philippine Basic Education Assessments and Reforms in the Past 100 Years, 1921-2020

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Abstract. With the sheer number of assessments done in the past one hundred years, Philippine education is one of the most studied sectors in the country. The most pivotal assessment is the Congressional Commission on Education, popularly known as the EDCOM 1991. The present government—from both the executive and legislative departments—is pursuing once again a comprehensive assessment of the Philippine education system (PES), as it confronts new challenges brought about by fast-changing times. In this historical research and systematic review, the authors cover the assessments of the PES that go back to the 1920s, with a focus on the report of the EDCOM 1991. The study uses path constitution analysis as the theoretical framework to analyze the evolution of education and governance in the past 100 years. Various methodologies, including desk review, historical research, document analysis, online public forums, focus group discussions, and key informant interviews were employed from March 2020 to December 2021. The results of this study aim to inform the plans and strategies adopted by the Department of Education, through its Education Futures Programme, as it opens the conversation on the future of the PES.

Keywords: Philippine education system, Philippine basic education, EDCOM 1991, path constitutional analysis, education assessments

Background and Rationale of the Study

Vision-setting for Philippine education was last done three decades ago, when the 1991 Congressional Commission on Education (EDCOM) came up with a comprehensive assessment. Several major assessments followed focusing on various aspects of the Philippine education system (PES): education governance, education finance, educational outcomes, and curricular reform. Just the sheer number of these studies makes the PES one of the most studied sectors in the country. The

reports, however, seem to be more preoccupied with finding what is wrong rather than what is right for the PES. This goes back to the lack of long-term vision that guides these assessments. This is not surprising as most of these studies were done by institutions outside the government, concerned perhaps with the lack of serious attention being given to the sector. Like what their forebears did 30 years ago, the present government—from both the executive and legislative departments—intends to once again make a comprehensive assessment of the PES through the passage of Senate Joint Resolution No. 10, “Creating a Congressional Oversight Committee on Education to Review and Assess Philippine Education,” on 10 December 2019. The main proponents of the resolution argue that the recommendations of the EDCOM of 1991 were either not acted upon or not implemented as originally intended. For example, the resolution noted the failure to create and institutionalize a permanent National Coordinating Council for Education (NCCE) that would harmonize the policies and programs of the Department of Education (DepEd), Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA), and Commission on Higher Education (CHED). The resolution also highlighted serious problems that continue to persist in the PES, such as the low net enrollment ratio for junior and senior high schools; low completion rate of junior high school; chronic shortages in teachers and classrooms; large class sizes; low levels of learning achievement; and low passing rate in licensure examinations (Senate Joint Resolution No. 10, 2019).

The Senate also cited continuing difficulties in the transition to the K to 12 curriculum since its implementation in 2013; the inability of the TESDA to fully implement the provisions of the law that created it by devolving technical and vocational education and training (TVET) to local governments and industry; and the inefficiencies brought about by the rapid increase in the number of state universities and colleges (SUCs) and local universities and colleges (LUCs) in the recent decades. The resolution likewise pointed out the need to focus on ensuring the quality and relevance of instruction and enhancing the capacity of higher education institutions to conduct meaningful research in light of the enactment of the following laws in the past few years: United Student Financial Assistance System for Tertiary Education (2015), Universal Access to Quality Tertiary Education Act (2017), and *Tulong Trabaho Act* (2019).

On the other hand, the DepEd has taken proactive measures by creating the Education Futures Programme (EducFutures) and initiating a review of the EDCOM 1991 Report. Aligned with it, the research team was tasked to undertake the review from March 2020 to December 2021, with two-fold primary objectives of evaluating the implementation status of the EDCOM’s legislative agendas and policy recommendations, and determining whether the implementation has resulted in the desired change or if other exogenous factors were overlooked either by the assessments or in the process of policy development in education. This study neither attempts to come up with a comprehensive assessment of the PES nor tries to provide an overarching vision for such an undertaking. Rather, it intends to look back into the report of the EDCOM of 1991 to provide context to current efforts that seek to do both. While this review of the EDCOM 1991 report will be the lynchpin of this undertaking, the study will also look back into the assessments that preceded and succeeded it. This historical research and systematic review will cover assessments

that go back to the 1920s, when the first major education survey, the Monroe Report, was undertaken. These include:

- Educational Survey Commission Report (Monroe Report) of 1925;
- Economic Survey Committee of 1927;
- Prosser Survey on Vocational Education of 1930;
- Commonwealth/Quezon Educational Survey of 1935;
- Joint Congressional Committee on Education Report of 1949;
- UNESCO Survey on Philippine Education of 1949;
- Swanson Survey of 1960;
- Survey of the Outcomes of Elementary Education, 1976;
- Philippine Education Sector Studies, 1988;
- *Making Education Work* (Report of the EDCOM of 1991) published in 1993;
- Presidential Commission on Educational Reform (PCER) Report of 2000;
- United Nations Human Development Programme (UNDP) *Human Development Report* (HDR) of 2008/2009;
- *Education Outcomes in the Philippines*, by the Asian Development Bank (2010);
- *The Nation's Journey to Greatness: Looking Beyond Five Decades of Philippine Education*, by Dumlao-Valisno (2012);
- *Philippine Education for All 2015 Review Report*, by the DepEd;
- *Assessing Basic Education Service Delivery in the Philippines: Public Education Expenditure Tracking and Quantitative Service Delivery Study*, by the World Bank and AusAid (2016); and
- *The 2020 Review of the Mandate/Functions, Management Systems, and Processes of Agencies in the Executive Branch: Education Sector*, commissioned by the Department of Budget and Management (DBM).

Objectives of the Study

This research aims to provide an analysis of the evolution of education governance based on the major assessments made on the PES in the past 100 years, specifically the basic education system, with a special focus on the report of the EDCOM of 1991. The results of this study aim to inform the plans and strategies adopted by the DepEd EducFutures, as it opens the conversation on the future of PES in the next 100 years. Specifically, the following are the study's objectives:

- Identify and analyze education governance issues and concerns;
- Determine the extent to which the target education outcomes for the year 2020 set by the EDCOM in 1991 were achieved;
- Systematically compile and curate findings, lessons, and recommendations that were integrated or not integrated into the governance structures, plans, policies, and reforms of the PES;
- Analyze how major policies adopted in the past have positively and negatively impacted desired outcomes of the PES; and
- Provide action and policy recommendations to EducFutures that could inform the unit in developing their plans and strategies for shaping the future of Philippine education.

Theoretical Framework and Methodology

This study uses path constitution analysis (PCA) as a theoretical framework for analyzing the evolution of education policies and governance in the past 100 years. PCA is a combination of concepts of path dependence and path creation (Garud & Karnøe, 2001) “wherein paths are seen as a mixture of emergent processes and deliberate actions” (Meyer & Schubert, 2007, p. 28). Path dependence and path creation frameworks argue that development is based on the decisions made in the past (Elsner et al., 2005). The PCA is a relatively new approach to understanding the historical development of technologies, institutions, and organizations (Sydow et al., 2012). The concept of path dependence “pays attention to the impact of past events” as well as “self-reinforcing processes that are triggered by one or more, often ‘small’ event” vis-à-vis the “primacy of optimal solutions in terms of efficiency...upon the course of the path’s future trajectory” (Sydow et al., 2012, p. 157). On the other hand, the concept of “path creation” emphasizes the “agency and collectivities of multiple, competent individual and/or organizational actors in particular, who coordinate their activities with each other” and whose actions lead to deviations from existing technological, institutional or organizational paths “even though they may not be proficient enough to initiate or control the deviation entirely” (Sydow et al., 2012, p. 158). Path constitution integrates path dependence and path creation and offers a constructivist understanding in which these concepts “are only two possible ways to build and transform a path in time and space” (Sydow et al., 2012, p. 158). Other ways of influencing a path include “intentional path defense or extension, unintended path dissolution, or breaking a path without creating a new one” (Sydow et al., 2012, p. 158).

In this study, the EDCOM 1991 is considered “path-dependent” and a “path-creator” because of its ten legislative agendas and eight policy recommendations that led to the subsequent developments in education policies and governance. Comprehending a process as complex and intricate as the evolution of the PES would be an enormous challenge if taken head-on. The study therefore focuses on the “deep-seated challenges” that have been hounding the country’s education system for most of its history, and follow how policies, governance structures, and processes have taken shape in response to these issues throughout the decades. We identify these persistent concerns as follows:

- institutional and governance challenges;
- inadequate financial resources for education;
- challenges in human resource development of teachers/educators;
- inequitable access to quality education; and
- responsiveness of the curriculum to socioeconomic transformations happening at the local and global levels.

In tracing path-dependent and path-creating elements, the researchers adopted various methods and engagements from March 2020 to December 2021. A desk review was conducted on the four volumes of the EDCOM report, including a review of key studies and major assessments preceding and succeeding its publication, a document analysis of post-EDCOM education policies, and the proposal for a Congressional

Oversight Committee on Education, as outlined in the Senate Joint Resolution No. 10 of the 18th Congress. Focus group discussions and semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders and the Education Futures Unit team, including the DepEd secretary and undersecretaries, were conducted online due to COVID-19 restrictions.

The researchers' initial findings on the review of the EDCOM 1991 were presented in an online public forum, "Revisiting EDCOM 1991" (DepEd, 2021), with the participation of policymakers, civil society groups, educators, basic education teachers, and officials from three agencies – the DepEd, CHed, and TESDA. Insights from panel reactors and forum participants have provided valuable insights to this research. In addition, the research team's active participation in various meetings and dialogues with committees and agencies, namely, the Committee on Basic Education, Arts, and Culture; Committee on Higher, Technical and Vocational Education; the DepEd Executive Committee; and the Senate Technical Working Group on EDCOM 2; and in the series of online workshops conducted by the PROMAN consulting company for the Technical Assistance for Development of the Education Sector Analysis (ESA) and Education Sector Plan (ESP) for Philippine Basic Education Plan 2030, significantly contributed to the overall analysis and recommendations.

Review of Related Literature

For the past century, numerous assessments have been done to trace the issues and concerns plaguing the Philippine education system (PES). Philippine education is a product of three eras of colonization and post-war history that shaped its culture and structure, referred to by De Guzman as the "dramatic changes in the various epochs of educational evolution" (2003, p. 39). An essential approach to understanding the continuities and discontinuities of the structural and curricular reforms in the Philippine education system is delving in the past and reflecting on works done (Rockwell, 2011). In this sense, understanding the intricate system of PES means looking back into the country's long history of drastic changes, beginning from its "unstructured origin" and how it has been continuously shaped and reshaped iteratively and recursively by historical events, global forces, and societal demands.

Periods of Cultural Influence and Development of Philippine Education

Understanding both present and future education entails examining strings of cause and effect of historical events. Studies and reports about the past and present scenarios of Philippine education have highlighted on the colonial impact on the country's education system, as emphasized by Cortes (1980) in her comparative study of ASEAN education systems. Cortes pointed out that the culture and structure of Philippine education is a reflection of four eras of colonization. For decades, it was taught in Philippine schools that the natives were illiterate and uncivilized, as claimed by Spanish explorers who landed on the island of Samar in 1521 (Aquino, 1993), based perhaps, on the prevailing education model in Europe. However, historical inquiries (Alzona, 1932; Aquino, 1993; LeRoy, 1903; Van Niel, 1993) proved that the natives of the islands, who would eventually become the "Filipinos," had a prosperous livelihood and, notably, an established education system. They have a system of writing with the existence of a seventeen-symbol *Baybayin* script written on indigenous materials (Alzona, 1932; Aquino, 1993; LeRoy, 1903; Van Niel, 1993) and "a system of laws or customs administered by the councils of old men" (LeRoy, 1903, p. 659). Tribal tutors

served as community teachers and every town had a temple with a collection of books in the form of palms, leaves, and bamboo under the custody of native priests (LeRoy, 1903). The subject content is that of history, legends, folklore, tales, statutes, deeds of versions, and poems. But related artifacts were destroyed, as they contradicted the colonizer's religious beliefs and ideologies (LeRoy, 1903).

Spanish colonization marked the "formalization" of the education system wherein elementary schools were said to be "present in every town and teachers were paid two dollars a month without board or lodging...reading and writing lessons were in Spanish, followed by Christian doctrine and casaysayan" (Jagor, 1875, as cited in Fox, 1965, p. 228). Filipino children during that era "learned to read a little, a few even more little, but they soon forget it again", and they "learned arithmetic, very quickly, generally aiding themselves by the use of mussels or stones, which they pile in little heaps before them and then count through" (Jagor, 1875, p. 169).

Finally, secondary high schools were established through the Education Decree of 1863, thus introducing a complete education system (DepEd, n.d.; Dacumos, 2013; Cortes, 1980) with two elementary schools for every municipality (Cortes, 1980). Spain's objectives were to "indoctrinate the natives with Christianity, to spread the Spanish language, and to foster the inculcation of Spanish culture" (Hardacker, 2013, p. 9). Despite its uneven implementation, the formal system equipped the Filipinos to "function outside of colonial rule" and created "a cadre of enlightened people" (Hardacker, 2013, p. 23) who sought to overthrow the colonial power—a result that opposed the expectations of the Spanish rulers of maintaining its colonial power in the archipelago. Eventually, the established schools gradually ceased during the revolution of Filipinos against Spanish tyranny.

The lack of a common language was the most prevailing issue identified during the Spanish era, which led to the teaching of the Spanish language to the natives. Despite these efforts, less than 4% of the population was educated enough to speak, read, and write in Spanish (Alzona, 1932). This underscores the historical pattern of unequal access to education dating back to the Spanish period, wherein only the privileged social class, i.e., the *ilustrados* and *mestizos* have access to education. This system persisted into the contemporary era where children in poverty, those with special needs, and those living in difficult contexts are deprived of their fundamental right to access quality education (PROMAN, 2021).

In his article "Education in the Philippines," George Counts (1925) referred to the Church and the priest as symbols of Spanish colonialism in the country, while the school and the teacher as symbols of American colonialism. It was during the onset of American occupation in 1898 that major revisions to the Spanish-instituted education system were immediately imposed (Barrows, 1910). "Schools were reopened in every part of the archipelago" and works carried out with intelligence and solicitude by military men during the "dreadful perplexing months of 1900 and the early part of 1901" where "officers commanding the garrisons of towns in all parts of the archipelago manifest their belief in a policy of native conciliation by the warmest support and advocacy of education" (Barrows, 1910, p. 160).

Prior to the 1925 Monroe Survey, David Barrow's published report in 1910 presented an overall account of the status of Philippine education, ten years after its operation under the American policy. He mentioned the strong support of Filipinos for the supervised system of public schools, citing an estimated 90 percent attendance

in public schools – “out of a population of perhaps 7,000,000, nearly 600,000 are in attendance” (Barrows, 1910, p.161). Also, a total of 8,210 Filipino teachers were trained, but the greatest task, according to Barrow, was training the Filipinos for leadership (Barrows, 1910), such that the demand to establish more secondary schools and a larger fund appropriation for education was necessary. It also justified the need to teach liberal and humanities courses along with already existing science and vocational training.

Introducing the American system of education in the Philippines, according to Casambre (1982, p. 7), was “pervasive and far-reaching,” and its hallmark was the creation of a curriculum aimed to homogenize and foster nationalism among the Filipinos. Francisco (2015) emphasized that:

The colonial education aimed to quell Filipino anti-colonial nationalism and facilitate obedience to the colonial state by casting good citizenship and proper patriotism in terms of economic self-sufficiency and non-violence, and by defining national allegiance as loyalty to both the Philippines and the U.S.; the American colonial curriculum encouraged Filipinos to think beyond the local and to make the nation their primary unit of loyalty. (p.1)

Interestingly, the American colonial government provided a major financial contribution, in which around 20% of the total government expenditure was spent on education in 1938. It was said to be the highest amount in Southeast Asia during the period, owing to the high literacy rate and enrolment compared with other Southeast Asian countries. It was a period in which the Philippines was described to be of the highest living standards (Van Sprang, 2016). However, despite the remarkable results, America’s experiment on Filipino education was confronted with problems and issues. The “inferior accomplishments” according to Count (1925) were the result of several causative factors. One of these is the language problem that was never encountered in American schools or schools of other countries (Count, 1925). This was further elaborated in the first major assessment of the Philippine education system chaired by Paul Monroe in 1925. Monroe (1925) emphasized the language problem as unique for three reasons: (1) there were numerous dialects in the islands; (2) there was no immediate prospect of any one of the local dialects becoming supreme to the other dialects, and (3) there was a low tendency to establishing a common language¹. Monroe (1925) claimed that a common language would provide Filipinos the capacity to communicate with the world at large, but building a national culture would be impossible because of its meagerness during that period. Appallingly, other unresolved issues and challenges during American colonization have persisted until today—problems related to teacher training, relevance of curriculum, and education facilities (Count, 1925; Monroe, 1925; Aldana, 1949; EDCOM 1991/1993; Dumlao-Valisno, 2012).

During the Japanese occupation from 1941 to 1944, public education was used as a tool for Filipinos to assimilate the Japanese culture. According to Dery (1984), Philippine education under Japanese rule was

the most effective means of realizing their goals. Japanese authorities utilized the educational system to the fullest. The Japanese authorities banked the upbringing of younger Filipino generations to the Japanese blueprint. Through it, the aim to eradicate all vestiges of Western influences in the Philippines could be gradually affected. (p. 313)

Japan introduced revisions to the curriculum. Tagalog and Nippongo were prescribed as the official languages, and the English language was abolished (Dery, 1984). Japan emphasized physical fitness and discipline. Children and youth were mandated to perform calisthenic movements broadcast over the radio, a program called “Radio *Taisyō*” (Jose & Yu-Jose, 1997, as cited in Utah State University, n.d.). Under Japanese rule, education aimed to promote friendly relations between Japan Philippines, the inculcation of an oriental mind, obliteration of Filipino overemphasis on materialism, elevation of people’s morals, love for labor, and promotion of vocational education (Dery, 1984).

Assessments and Reforms from 1925 to 2020

Since the Monroe Survey in 1925, various assessments and studies on the Philippine education system have been undertaken. These endeavors not only contributed to the expansive understanding of the system but have also served as pivotal points for tracing paths in the PES based on their findings and recommendations (see Table 1). Magno (2010) presented three phases of educational assessments: (a) national studies during the early years, i.e., the Monroe Survey, the Research and Evaluation and Guidance Division of the Bureau of Public Schools, the Economic Survey Committee, the Prosser Survey, and the UNESCO survey; (b) the contemporary period, which covered the EDCOM in 1991, “the Fund for Assistance to Private Organization (FAPE), and the creation of the Center for Educational Measurement (CEM), and the Asian Psychological Services Assessment Corporation (APSA),” and a period of future directions that focused on researches on educational assessment, measurement, and evaluation, that brought impact on national policy development and “creation of associations” (Magno, 2010, p. 140).

Figure 1
Expenditure per Child of Primary Age
Primary Education Expenditure per Child in USD (PPP)

Source. World Bank and UIS (2022)³

The Congressional Commission on Education (EDCOM) 1991

In 1991, the EDCOM published its first assessment report titled *Making Education Work: An Agenda for Reform*. It was in 1993 that its entire report was published and compiled into four books spanning 11 volumes (see Table 1) and approximately 3,260 pages. At the heart of the EDCOM study were the 12 legislative agendas (see Table 2) and eight policy recommendations (see Table 3) that were pivotal to the major structural changes in the Philippine education system. While some of the recommendations were immediately acted upon, such as the creation of the TESDA and CHed, the recommendations that were tightly connected to the issues and were repeatedly identified in the past took a much longer time before they were implemented. Out of the 12 legislative agendas, four were not implemented but were, in terms of aim, directly and indirectly reflected in the DepEd's policies and development plans, including the implementation of Republic Act (RA) 10533, which reformed the K-10 basic education system into the present K to 12 curriculum, and the institutionalization of the school-based management (SBM) system through RA 9155.

Table 1
*Major Assessments on Philippine Education System, 1925-2020:
Findings and Recommendations*

Date	Report/Study	Findings/Recommendations
1925	Monroe Survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highly centralized administration of the public school system • Teachers were not professionally trained • Need to use vernacular as the medium of instruction for teaching character education
1927	Economic Survey Committee	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emphasis on vocational education • Training of intelligent, civic-minded homemakers, skilled workers, and artisans • Secondary education that is aligned to agriculture, trades, industry, commerce, and home economics
1930	Prosser Survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highly centralized administration of the public system • Teachers were not professionally trained • Vernacular as the medium of instruction for teaching character
1935	Commonwealth Education Survey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to emphasize adult education • Need to emphasize agricultural education • Issue on language of instruction • Character and citizenship education • Emphasis on vocational education • Recognition of women's rights
1949	Joint Congressional Committee on Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to emphasize adult education • Restore the full-day school and the 7th grade

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| 1949 | UNESCO Survey | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National policies to use English as the primary medium of instruction, to offer Spanish in high schools and permit teachers to use their own dialect when teaching • Need for more effective elementary education • Restoration of the full-day session in all elementary schools • Lengthen elementary and secondary programs from 10 to 12 years • Attention to adult education • Need emphasis on community schools • Need to conduct thorough surveys as a basis for long-range planning • Strengthen teacher education • Decentralize administration |
| 1960 | Swanson Survey | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reiterated the results of the Monroe survey • Notable problems in the education of minorities • Poor financing • Prioritize investments in primary education and strengthen secondary education • Restore the 7th grade |
| 1976 | Survey of the Outcomes of Elementary Education | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sixth-grade students' achievement was less than 50% mastery on all subjects |
| 1988 | Philippine Education Sector Studies | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Problem areas in sector management; establish a congressional commission on education • Weak planning and budgeting process • Significant drop-out rate • Poor teacher quality • Inefficient and untimely production of textbooks |
| 2000 | Presidential Commission for Educational Reform (PCER) | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve quality of teacher training • Establish a congressional education commission • Examine bilingual policy |
| 2009 | UNDP Human Development Report | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partial implementation of the decentralized governance of basic education (RA 1955) through the school-based management system • Inadequate policy formulation in the area of learning and pedagogy (unresolved medium of instruction) • Substantiate, operationalize, and implement the Basic Education Sector Reform Agenda (BESRA) as framework for all reform in Philippine basic education |
| 2010 | Education Outcomes in the Philippines by the ADB | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Major performance setback of basic education • Disparity in education • Counter-effective policies, e.g., Magna Carta for Teachers, and the pupil/student population-bias allocation of classroom construction under the Fair and Equitable Allocation of the DECS for Capital Outlay Act • Lack of program evaluation |

2012	The Nation's Journey to Greatness: Looking Beyond Five Decades of Philippine Education (Dumlao-Valisno, 2012)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevant school experience to attain ability-driven education through universal access to education, delivery of quality K to programs, improve teacher and leadership quality, establish systematic and credible assessment system as a quality assurance mechanism, and improve education governance • Resolve political and socioeconomic systems through active involvement of LGUs, increase investment in public education • Scale up school-based management systems and strengthen public-private partnership in education
2015	Philippine Education for All Review Report	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need for revisions of the basic education curriculum • Revisit the Philippine EFA and targets • Monitoring scheme from the regional level to the national level
2016	Assessing Basic Education Delivery in the Philippines: Public Education Expenditure Tracking and Quantitative Service Delivery Study	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved teacher hiring efforts but weak teacher allocation systems resulting to inefficient teacher deployment • Inadequate teacher professional development systems • Improved key school facilities but classroom deficits still existed • Lack of school sanitation facilities • Limited school discretionary funding • Weak school-level accountability • Significant differences in levels of education spending • Resource-constrained schools in poor communities
2020	Review of the Mandate/ Functions, Management Systems and Processes of Agencies in Executive Branch	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a Human Capital Development Committee (HCDC) • Re-establish the National Coordinating Council for Education • Transfer the relevant offices of the DepEd, CHED, and TESDA to the Philippine Qualifications Framework - National Coordinating Council (PQF-NCC) Permanent Secretariat • Abolish the National Book Development Board • Abolish the National Council for Children's Television (NCCT), and alternatively convert the NCCT into a non-governmental organization • Open more Philippine High School for the Arts campuses nationwide • Transfer the National Museum into the umbrella of the National Commission for Culture and the Arts for administrative and budgeting processes • Clarify the delineation of functions between the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) and the Office of the Executive Director • Create an internal audit unit in the CHED • Merge/Amalgamate SUCs to create a regional university system • Strengthen the agricultural extension functions of SUCs • Conduct a study on the possible merger of DOST and the CHED • Strengthen the role of DepEd in managing the Special Education Fund (SEF)

Note. This figure was constructed from various sources of data.

Table 2
EDCOM Book Titles and Volumes

Parts of the 1991 EDCOM Report	Title	Volume Title
Book 1	Areas of Concern in Philippine Education	Volume 1: Education and Manpower Development Programs Volume 2: Teacher Welfare, Compensation and Benefits Volume 3: Sectoral Targets and Functional Linkages Volume 4: Governance and Management
Book 2	The Educational Ladder	Volume 1: Basic Education Volume 2: Post-Secondary Education and Training Volume 3: Tertiary Education
Book 3	Consultative Reports	Volume 1: What the Public Perceive: Regional and Provincial Consultations (with Annex) Volume 2: What the Experts Say: Sectoral Consultations
Book 4	Technical Studies	Volume 1: Position Papers and Reports of Educators and Sectoral Representatives Volume 2: Reports of Consultants and Experts in Education

Table 3
The 12 Legislative Agendas of the EDCOM 1991

Legislative Agenda	Status*	Date Implemented	Annotation
1. Concurrent resolution urging the DECS to lengthen the school calendar	I	July 25, 1994	RA 7797 An act to lengthen the school calendar from two hundred days (200) to not more than two hundred twenty (220) days
2. Converting all secondary schools into general high schools	NI	-	
3. Upgrade the quality of the teaching profession, prescribing a licensure exam	I	December 16, 1994	RA 7836 "Philippine Teacher Professionalization Act of 1994", an act to strengthen the regulation and supervision of the practice of teaching in the Philippines and prescribing a licensure examination for teachers and for other purposes
4. Upgrading the minimum Salary Grade level of public-school teachers	PI		

5. Strengthen teacher education by establishing centers of excellence	I		RA 7784 An act to strengthen teacher education in the Philippines by establishing centers of excellence, creating a Teacher Education Council
6. Institutionalizing Early Childhood Care and Development (ECCD)	I	December 5, 2022	RA 8980 “ECCD Act”, an act promulgating a comprehensive policy and a national system of early childhood care and development, providing funds therefor
7. Concurrent resolution enjoining DECS to create non-traditional but cost-effective economical modes of instruction	NI	-	-
8. An act creating a national testing and evaluation agency	NI	-	-
9. An act creating a Center for Leading Edge Educational	NI	-	-
10. An act creating the Education Statistics Division in the NSO	NI	-	-
11. An act creating the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority, providing powers, structure, and for other purposes	I	August 25, 1994	RA 7796 “TESDA Act of 1994”
12. An act creating the Commission on Higher Education (CHED), appropriating funds, thereof and for other purposes	I	May 18, 1994	RA 7722 “Higher Education Act of 1994”

*I – Implemented; NI – Not Implemented; PI – Partially Implemented

Table 4
The Eight Policy Recommendations of the EDCOM 1991

Policy Recommendations	Status	Date Implemented	Annotation
1. The goal of elementary education is progressive functional literacy	PI	-	-
2. The goal of secondary education is preparation for college for the world of work, thus, secondary schools should consist of a junior high school and two-year senior high school	I		RA 10533 An act enhancing the Philippine basic education system by strengthening its curriculum and increasing the number of years for basic education, appropriating funds therefore and for other purposes
3. An act mandating a language of instruction policy for basic education	I		DO 74, s. 2009 “Institutionalizing Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) Articulated in R.A. 10533 or the “Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013”
4. Revision of the preservice education curriculum for the above reforms in basic education	NI	-	-
5. Adoption of a policy of teacher and school accountability for pupil learning	NI	-	-
6. Involvement of community and parents in education. Schools should encourage parental and community involvement in education	I		DO. 54, s. 1999 Revised guidelines governing parents-teachers associations (PTA)
7. Urging DECS and the Department of Budget and Management (DBM) to consistently accord the highest priority in allocating education budget to basic education	I		Section 5, Article 14 of the 1987 Constitution “The state shall assign the highest budgetary priority to education and ensure the teaching will attract and retain rightful share of the best talents through adequate remuneration and other means of job satisfaction and fulfillment”

8. Resolution urging the DECS and DBM to give priority to allocating education budget to the Madaris and mission schools	PI	DO 81, s. 2007 Assistance to private madrasah: An incentive to adopt the standard curriculum as authorized under DO 51., s. 2004 and total mainstreaming of madrasah education as a component of the national system of basic education DO 57, s. 2010 Implementation of the basic education madrasah Programs for Muslim out-of-school youth and adults DO 41, s. 2017 Policy guidelines on madrasah education in the K to 12 Basic Education Program
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*I – Implemented; NI – Not Implemented; PI – Partially Implemented

Discussion of Findings

Categorized according to the challenges, the following are the current status of the proposed legislations related to the EDCOM 1991, and the issues they intended to address:

Institutional and Governance Challenges

1. An act creating the Commission on Higher Education, appropriating funds thereof, and for other purposes.

On 18 May 1994, RA 7722 or the Higher Education Act created CHed to oversee higher education in the country. Along with the creation of TESDA, the three agencies—the DepEd, CHed, and TESDA—have led to the present trifocal system of education. Efficient and effective learning delivery and administration were expected from the trifocal system, but the setup failed to achieve coordination, and the decentralization of basic education, higher education, and vocational education became a driver of inequality, with the CHed being structurally placed at the apex and the Department of Education, Culture and Sports (DECS) at the base (Dumlao-Valisno, 2012). Twenty-seven years since the trifocal education system was conceived, teacher education has remained an educational gap, with the DepEd having a very minimal role in pre-service education and training. The EDCOM agenda of creating a National Coordinating Council for Education (NCCE) was formalized in 2000 through EO 273, which is supposed to bring coherence and coordinated decisions from the agencies, but the council has never progressed. Dumlao-Valisno (2013) pointed out that the best option to harmonize the three agencies was to institute a flat coordination mechanism and to “recognize the authority of the secretary of education to orchestrate education-related matters” as mandated by law – as chair of CHed (RA 7722), chair of the Teacher Education Council (RA 7784), and as co-chair of DOLE and the TESDA Board (Dumlao-Valisno, 2013, p. 375).

2. An act creating the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority, providing for its powers, structure, and for other purposes.

The TESDA was established through the enactment of RA 7796 on 25 August 1994. The agency was the fusion of the National Manpower and Youth Council (NMYC) of the Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE), the Bureau of Technical and Vocational Education (BTVE) of the DECS, and the Apprentice Program of the Bureau of Local Employment (BLE), also under DOLE. The merging of these offices was meant to reduce the overlapping of skills development activities initiated by various public-private sector agencies and to provide direction to the country's technical-vocation education training (TVET) system. TESDA's mandate is to (i) integrate, coordinate, and monitor skills development programs; (ii) restructure efforts that will promote and develop middle-level personnel; (iii) approve skill standards and tests; (iv) develop an accreditation system for institutions involved in middle-level personnel development; (v) fund programs and projects for technical education and skills development; and (vi) assist trainers' training program.

3. An act converting all secondary schools, except all existing science high schools, the Philippine Science High School and the Philippine School for the Arts, into general high schools.

This legislation was never enacted, but before the implementation of the K to 12 basic education curricula, secondary education had four year levels that were based on the American schooling system. This old system now pertains to junior high school or grades 7 to 10 under the new curriculum. The upper specialized high school system is now the senior high school or grades 11 and 12.

4. A concurrent resolution urging the Department of Education, Culture and Sports (DECS) to lengthen the school calendar from 185 days to 200 days, and granting provincial superintendents the authority to determine the beginning and end of the school calendar, taking peculiar circumstances of a given community.

EDCOM's recommendation to lengthen the school calendar of elementary and high school was based on the perspective that a longer instructional period could improve the learners' performance, as in the case of developed countries like Germany and Japan (EDCOM, 1993). Thus, on 25 August 1994, this recommendation was made into law through RA 7797. The law has also granted provincial superintendents the authority to determine the start and end of a school year in times of a "peculiar circumstance" in their respective communities.

During the early months of the COVID-19 outbreak, Section 3 of RA 7797 was amended on 17 July 2020, to mandate the Secretary of Education to recommend to the President adjustments in the school calendar "in times of emergency". Moreover, the school opening was also changed from its traditional period in June into August through DO 7, s. 2020, such that, the number of school days was consequently changed to 230 days per school year. The adjustments were made to address the learning gaps and to give teachers the much-needed time to prepare the learning materials for the online and remote modes of teaching and learning. The decision, however, has overlooked the probability of a very high heat index, especially in March, April, and May, posing risks to both the students and teachers if they are to attend classes and perform outdoor school activities during those months in summer.

The length of a school calendar or the number of instructional days in a school year was said to be an effective policy for increasing student achievement (Hincapie, 2016; Patall, et al., 2010;) but the National Center of Education and the Economy (NCEE) claims that the best education systems in the world implement 175-220 school-days policy. According to the NCEE, the variation of school days among the best-performing education systems in the world suggests that the quality of time spent in the classroom is a determining factor in student performance.

Challenges in Human Resource Development of Teachers/Educators

1. An act to upgrade the quality of the teaching profession, strengthen the regulations governing the practice of teaching in the Philippines, and prescribe a licensure examination for teachers, and for other purposes.

EDCOM's recommendation to upgrade and strengthen the quality of the teaching profession and to strengthen the regulations governing the practice of teaching in the Philippines led to the enactment of RA 7836 or the Philippine Teachers Professionalization Act of 1994. This law replaced the Professional Board of Teachers (PBET) with the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET), and it transferred the authority for the conduct of the qualifying examination for teachers from the Civil Service Commission to the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC). At present, the LET is the only institutionalized tool used to assess the preparedness and competence of Filipino teacher candidates. Twenty-nine years after its implementation, emerging concerns include the need to evaluate and review its relevance, appropriateness, and technical quality, and to consider an alternative assessment of pre-teachers.

For the in-service teachers, two pressing concerns are related to continuing professional education (CPE): (1) proliferation of private training entities that provide CPE credit units; and (2) teachers' "beyond human capacity" workload (Tomacruz, 2018). The CPE units are a requirement for the renewal of the license of PRC-licensed professionals. It is based on the Continuing Professional Development Act of 2016 (RA 10912), which authorized the PRC to require 45 credit units in the form of training from PRC-accredited CPD providers, or, through continuing education, i.e., graduate programs (Section 5). However, teachers are faced with overwhelming non-teaching tasks that they describe as "beyond human capacity." Thus, they no longer have the time to attend training and other professional development activities.

On the other hand, Section 3 of RA 10912, or the nature of CPD programs, is ambiguous in terms of implementation because the units earned from graduate programs are not recognized by the implementing agency. CPD activities as defined in Section 3 pertain to (a) formal learning, (b) non-formal learning, (c) informal learning, (d) self-directed learning, (e) online learning activities, and (f) professional work experience. Moreover, "formal learning" was defined in the act as the "educational arrangements such as the curricular qualifications and teaching-learning requirements that take place in education and training institutions recognized by relevant national authorities, and which lead to diplomas and qualifications." Thus, graduate programs should be counted as a formal process of earning CPD units.

2. An act upgrading the minimum salary grade level of qualified school teachers in the elementary and secondary levels from Salary Grade 10 to Salary Grade 17.

This was drawn from the lack of implementation of the Magna Carta for Public School Teachers (RA 4670), specifically, Sections 14, 15, 16, 18, and 19 of the said law. The Magna Carta for Teachers was created to provide the public school teachers their professional rights and security. But 57 years after its passage, it has now “exhibited weaknesses that hampered the improvement of the social and economic status, as well as the working conditions of public school teachers” (Llego, n.d.). The upgrading of teacher salaries was recommended by the EDCOM as part of professionalizing the basic education force (EDCOM, 1993). Senate Bill 69 and House Bill 3676 were introduced on 30 June 2007 and 8 August 2019, respectively, to upgrade the teachers’ salary grade level as a measure to help them sustain the presently high cost of living.

Teachers’ salary was increased following the final tranche of the Salary Standardization Act of 2019 (RA 11466). The basic monthly salary of Teacher I is now PHP20,754, per DepEd Order 201. But in comparison to other qualified professionals in government service, and with the enormous administrative and teaching tasks that they fulfill daily (Arzadon, 2017; Geronimo & Campoamor-Olegario, 2020), the salary increase for teachers is still not enough to sustain their personal and family needs.

3. An act to strengthen teacher education in the Philippines by establishing centers of excellence, and appropriating funds thereof.

The recommendation of the EDCOM to uplift the quality of teacher education has transpired through the enactment of RA 7784 and the centers of excellence (COE) for teacher education were established, along with the creation of the Teacher Education Council (TEC). The TEC is mandated to “identify and designate among existing private and public schools, teacher education institutions as centers of excellence for teacher education at the national, regional, and provincial levels” and “to initiate a periodic review of curricula programs for teacher education and training through participatory methods, such as self-assessment by institutions” (Sec. 7). As an overseer of higher education, the CHED manages the pre-teacher education program and the CHED chairperson serves as an ex-officio member of the council and at the same time, as chair of the strengthened TEC’s pre-service Teacher Education Committee (Gonong et al., 2020, p.2).

In the CHED report dated 8 May 2018, there are 34 COEs for teacher education. Nineteen (19) are private higher education institutions (HEIs) and 15 are public HEIs. Meanwhile, there are 38 centers of development (COD) on teacher education, of which 18 are private HEIs and 20 are public HEIs (CHED, 2018). COEs and CODs for teacher education may need to be reviewed in terms of their performance in the LET and by the percentage of their pre-service teachers who pursued the teaching profession after graduation (Ladia et al., 2012). Moreover, a proposed legislation in the 18th Congress, Senate Bill 1887, was filed on 14 October 2020, calling for a reform of the selection process of COEs and CODs for teacher education.

Table 5

Total Number of Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs) recognized as Center of Excellence (COE) and Center of Development (COD) by Region, as of 8 May 2018

Region	Public		Private		Total
	COE	COD	COE	COD	
01 - Ilocos Region	2	3	1	1	7
02 - Cagayan Valley	1	1	2	-	4
03 - Central Luzon	2	2	1	1	6
04 - CALABARZON	-	3	3	1	7
05 - Bicol Region	1	2	1	1	5
06 - Western Visayas	1	1	-	3	5
07 - Central Visayas	1	2	1	1	5
08 - Eastern Visayas	-	2	-	-	2
09 - Zamboanga Peninsula	-	2	1	-	3
10 - Northern Mindanao	1	2	1	2	6
11 - Davao Region	1	-	1	3	5
12 - SOCCSKSARGEN	-	-	-	1	1
13 - National Capital Region	2	-	5	2	9
14 - Cordillera Administrative Region	1	-	2	1	4
15 - Autonomous Region of Muslim Mindanao	-	-	-	-	-
16 - CARAGA	1	-	-	1	2
17 - MIMAROPA	1	-	-	-	1
Total	15	20	19	18	72

Note. Data source is from the CHED Memorandum Order 3, s. 2019, “Distribution of Centers of Excellence/Development in Teacher Education by Region and Sector,” p. 33.

The establishment of the TEC and CHed’s management over pre-service teacher education is a consequence of the trifocal education system after the EDCOM 1991 recommendations, described by a former DepEd Secretary as “one of the educational gaps on teacher curriculum” that calls for a need for the DepEd to know how universities and colleges train education majors, and to strengthen the link between the pre-service and the in-service teachers.

Inequitable Access to Quality Education

1. An act institutionalizing early childhood care and development centers for children aged zero to six, creating the implementing machinery thereof, providing guidelines, incentives, government financial support, technical assistance, and for other purposes.

RA 8980, an act promulgating a comprehensive policy and national system for early childhood care and development (ECCD), was approved on 2 December 2000.

This act was created to resolve related issues identified in the EDCOM Report such as the lack of access for young children to early childhood education, especially those from the remote and depressed rural communities. ECCD was a major poverty intervention program that was developed to guarantee children's rights and to ensure their well-being (Manuel & Gregorio, 2011). The ECCD Council is mandated by RA 10410, or the Early Years Act of 2013, to implement the national government's ECCD system. The ECCD programs cover health, nutrition, early education, and social services for children ages 0-4 years. In addition, the council is also responsible for developing policies and programs, providing technical assistance and support to ECCD service providers, and monitoring ECCD service benefits and outcomes. Executive Order 778 transformed the Council for the Welfare of Children into the Early Childhood Care and Development Council on 13 January 2009; and Executive Order 806 issued on 8 June 2009 affirmed the role of the ECCD Council for the Welfare of Children (CWC).

Poor nutrition, limited early education, lack of appropriate psychosocial care, and inadequate protection for Filipino children, are still among the pressing concerns that call for serious attention. Since the early 1900s, the Philippine government has been working on an educational campaign on nutrition prevention and control of epidemic diseases, and care and feeding of young children, but more efforts have to be made to achieve zero hunger and zero malnutrition in the country. Based on the United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF) ranking in 2019, the Philippines ranked 9th in the world for having the most stunted children at 3.6 million, or nearly 30% of the total population of Filipino children under five years old (UNICEF, 2019).

Responsiveness of the Curriculum to Socioeconomic Transformations

1. An act creating the Center for Leading-Edge Educational Technologies

The proposed creation of this center was never implemented. There were several proposals from former Senator Edgardo Angara, such as Senate Bill 1091, titled "an act creating the Center for Leading-Edge Educational Technologies," which was proposed on 30 June 2004, and the Senate Bill 2581, or the "Charter of the Center for Leading-Edge Educational Technologies (CLEET)", proposed on 8 November 2010. Based on these proposals, "the CLEET will train educators, trainers, and practitioners from across the nation to influence the direction of educational technology on the premise that educational priorities should lead, rather than react, to the development of affordable educational technologies. The goal was to assemble a high-technology facility for accessing leading-edge hardware, software, and materials and a core of leadership to determine these priorities and to bring technology to bear on them as appropriate. The priorities will be areas of manpower developments and the educational curricula that are of broad importance and that are amenable to the educational promise of technology" (Senate Bill 2581). The Center for Leading Edge Educational Technology was supposed to serve a crucial role in the Philippine education sector.

Analysis and Recommendations

Several years of reform have been identified by various studies on Philippine education system conducted through the years (1925-2020), including the EDCOM 1991/1993. But the same deep-seated concerns have existed, described by Doronilla

and Cortes (2000) as a “perplexing and disturbing result” and “reforms that failed to transform” (Bautista et al., 2008/2009). The reforms failed to produce responsible, productive, and self-fulfilling citizens, as intended by the EDCOM 1991.

Considered holistic and highly significant, the EDCOM set the country’s education goals for the year 2000: (1) an education that is anchored on the principle of equity, quality, and empowerment; (2) equipping all Filipinos from 12 years old and above, with the essential skills, knowledge, and values through universal and relevant basic education; (3) a quality education for all; (4) an education that proactively responds to future needs and development; (5) a coordinated and balanced lifelong learning in both formal and informal education; and (6) a national education that recognizes diverse culture and international solidarity. It is important to note that, a year ahead of the EDCOM, the global community has called for a commitment to attain quality basic education for all (EFA) in the year 2015. As a UN member state, the Philippines strived to achieve the global commitment. Consequently, a package of policy reforms known as the Basic Education Sector Reform Agenda (BESRA) has been pursued by DepEd, with policy actions that were anchored on its five key reform thrusts: (1) get all schools to continuously improve; (2) enable teachers to further enhance their contribution to learning outcomes; (3) increase social support to the attainment of desired learning outcomes; (4) improve impact on outcomes from complementary early childhood education, alternative learning systems, and private sector participation; and (5) change institutional culture of the DepEd to improve the reform thrusts. The present K to 12 curricula under RA 10533 or the Basic Education Act of 2013 were rooted in BESRA 2006-2010 (Alonzo, 2015). A 10-year EFA Philippine Plan of Action covering the years 1991 to 2000 was also crafted and implemented, and it had “articulated the country’s national goals, objectives, policies, and strategies, and program implementations at the regional level” (DepEd, 2008, p. 3).

However, in terms of achieving the desired outcomes for Philippine education, figures suggest a continuing decline in both the quality and equal access to education. Based on the latest data from the World Bank, 91% of Filipino children at a late primary age are in learning poverty. A child in learning poverty is unable to read and understand a short, age-appropriate text by ten years old (World Bank & the UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2022). Learning poverty is an SDG 4 indicator that combines the share of primary-aged children and out-of-school youth who are schooling-deprived (SD)², and the share of pupils below a minimum proficiency in reading, who are learning-deprived (LD). In terms of learning deprivation, 90% of students in the Philippines did not achieve the minimum proficiency level (MPL) by the end of their primary school, and five percent of primary school-aged children were excluded from learning in school (World Bank & the UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2022).

Public spending on education is believed to increase economic growth based on its rate of social return. However, as of May 2021, the primary education expenditure per child of primary education age in the Philippines was USD 569 (Figure 5), which is 83.5% below the average for the East Asia and Pacific region, and 29.5% below the average for lower middle-income countries. Inadequate facilities, including classrooms, sanitation, access to water, electricity, and ICT were also noted in a recent study on basic education infrastructure. Navarro (2022) highlighted the government’s

lack of investment in school water, sanitation, and health facilities, electrification, and computer access, as compared to other Southeast Asian regions. On electrical connections alone, there are 1,562 schools with no connections yet and 39,335 schools needing upgrade since 2020 (Navarro, 2022).

Common Understanding of the Needs of the Philippine Education System

Given all the initiatives and efforts from various actors and institutions to attain a quality, relevant education system, along with its careful planning and exhaustive assessments in the past one hundred years, Philippine education has remained overwhelmed by complex challenges and uncertainties, like the COVID-19 pandemic and the endless evolving technology, such as machine learning trends and artificial intelligence that are creating new forms of learning spaces and tools. We have remained in the same state of searching for the perfect means of alleviating the education crisis that we have experienced since the colonial days. We are left with the same essential questions on the kind of education system that will work for both the present and the future, an education that is relevant to both global and local demands, and in accordance with its aim of a holistic development of the individual.

We need a common understanding of the needs of the Philippine education system, particularly, the basic education system; and the need to make decisions effectively in a coordinated manner. Looking back at the EDCOM 1991 and other major assessments done in the past, there was an enormous delay in the implementation of ambitious objectives, done at different stages of time, such that “the chances of failure before implementation are already lurking in the background” (Briones, personal communication, 2021).

Policymakers should build on the hard-earned gains over the past centuries. Continuities should be inclined towards a sharper and more focused agenda for EDCOM II that is anchored on the six education concerns: governance structures and institutions, resources and mobilization for education, human resource development, inequitable access, a responsive curriculum, and imperative glocalization and cooptation. Thus, we recommend the following actions:

1. Revisit the governance structure and institutions and the far-reaching implications of the trifocalized Philippine education system;
2. Consider decentralization and strengthening of the school-based management system (SBM);
3. Provide the highest budgetary priority to education and equally prioritize the subsectors in the education sector;
4. Provide continuing professional development programs for teachers that are aligned with the vision of the ASEAN community by providing sufficient time and funding, and management training for principals and short-term scholarships abroad for teachers; and
5. Strengthen quality assurance mechanisms.

It is also imperative that decisions employ futures-thinking perspectives; thus, the institutionalization of a futures lab under the DepEd must be given utmost attention. Finally, reforms must be anchored on Sustainable Development Goals 2030

and Ambisyon Natin 2040. As the Senate and House resolutions and our experience over the past hundred years have shown, the process of solicitude and reform in the education sector continues.

Endnotes

¹ “[T]he use of the dialects would doom the child to a narrow environment which in most cases would restrict his thought and life” (Monroe Survey, p. 24).

² The learning poverty indicator illustrates progress towards SDG 4.1.1b, which specifies that all children at the end of primary reach at least a minimum proficiency level (MPL) in reading (World Bank and the UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2022).

³ The primary education expenditure per child is calculated as the total expenditure on primary education divided by the total number of children of primary school age. Data for the Philippines is from 2009 (World Bank & the UIS, 2022).

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